

ASSESSMENT OF ACCURACY OF FIBRE ORIENTATION MEASUREMENT USING X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Non-destructive testing using X-ray computed tomography (CT) has proven to be a powerful tool for qualitative and quantitative characterisation of filled polymers. The question that has not been addressed yet is the accuracy of the published quantifications. This work deals with the 3D characterisation of glass fibres in a polypropylene matrix. The focus lies on the determination of fibre orientation by means of tensor representation. High resolution CT was applied using a laboratory system together with an in-house developed data analysis tool.

The paper shows results about accuracy of the developed method by comparing the results with ground truth data. In a second part the method is compared to the destructive standard method of sectioning and light optical image analysis.

High accuracy of more than 93% was observed at 2 μm voxel edge length. The influence of resolution is higher on length distribution but very small on orientation within the chosen range of voxel edge lengths. For the comparison of 2D and 3D method the orientation tensor elements are shown as values over sheet thickness at 21 positions. The samples show a distinct core-shell layered structure. By visualizing the tensors as ellipsoids, it is possible to get an impression about degree and direction of orientation. Both methods deliver almost the same values at every position. Values for mean tensors of the complete volumes under investigation show deviations below 0.007.

The results indicate that CT delivers accurate and valid results of fibre orientation. The advantages compared to the standard methods is the non-destructive manner, the volumetric analysis, the complete tensor representation and the fact, that additional information like fibre length distribution can be determined from the on single analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

X-Ray computed tomography (CT) is nowadays widely used for scientific and industrial applications. Many laboratory CT devices are installed for non-destructive testing (NDT) of materials and metrology. At the beginning, the value of analysing slice-images visually or semi-automatically was high enough. In recent years quantitative analyses came more and more into focus. This requires CT systems with resolutions that are compatible with the material to characterise, software for data analysis and calibration methodology. If a standard method exists for the determination of the feature under investigation, a comparison of the CT method with the standard method is useful.

Using high resolution laboratory CT systems that can reach resolutions down to 1 μm makes it possible to investigate filled polymeric systems. Several publications use Synchrotron radiation which is not be considered in this paper. For chopped fibre reinforced materials, attempts were made to extract the information of orientation and length distribution which are the most important parameters for reinforcement. In some papers the accuracy of the results was discussed mainly by comparing with simulation or modelled data [1-3]. The measurement of orientation using Synchrotron scans and a grey value based algorithm on carbon fibre filled PA was discussed in [4]. CT was used as experimental

method to measure orientation and to combine this information with mechanical or physical properties [5-7]. However the question about accuracy of orientation measurement on a laboratory system was not answered thoroughly. The reported problems using CT analysis were mainly poor contrast between fibres and matrix, lack of commercially available software and problems in separating fibres.

The motivation of this paper is to present a method for the quantitative characterisation of short fibre composite materials that allows for the investigation of single fibres and is therefore capable of producing tensor results. The accuracy is determined by comparison with ground truth data and with the standard method of 2D sectioning and LOM analysis.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The investigated material was polypropylene filled with 30 % by weight glass fibres. The nominal fibre diameter was 12.5 μm .

Cut- outs from multi- purpose test specimens with cross section of 10 by 4 mm^2 , which were produced by injection moulding, were scanned for the analysis of accuracy. CT data analysis was performed on parts of the scanned volumes in order to characterise approx. 250 fibres.

For comparisons of CT data with data from 2D sectioning, a sector shaped sheet with 2 mm thickness was produced by injection moulding (Fig. 1). At two positions (2 and 4) with different distance to the gate, specimens were cut- out and scanned. Three specimens were investigated per position for statistical reasons. The same specimens were grinded and analysed by a light optical method. The angles φ and θ were defined referring to [8] where the axes notation is X, Y and Z instead of 2, 1 and 3. Z indicates the direction of injection which is the expected preferred fibre orientation.

Figure 1: Geometry of sector shaped sheet showing positions of analysis 2 and 4

2.2 CT parameters and data analysis

The scans were performed at a μCT device Nanotom 180NF (GE phoenix|x-ray). Three different voxel edge lengths were chosen for the analysis of accuracy. Other CT scanner settings like tube voltage, integration time and number of projections were chosen as 80 kV, 750 ms and 1700 for all scans. These parameters lead to a scan-time of 129 minutes. The voxel edge lengths were verified by scanning a calibrated ball-bar specimen before each specimen scan.

The sector specimens were scanned applying 2 μm voxel edge length and the same parameters as stated above with the following difference. Because the size of the specimens was increased in order to get more information at each position, the detector was virtually increased by a factor of two. This required an increased number of projections (1900) for optimized data quality, resulting in increased scan time of 358 minutes. The specimens were aligned on the turntable in a way that the preferred fibre orientation was parallel to the rotation axis. This guarantees for more homogeneous penetration throughout 360° rotation and leads to better data quality.

CT data analysis was conducted using two software tools: the commercially available VG Studio MAX 2.2 (Volume Graphics, Germany) and the in house development iAnalyse [9]. VG Studio was used to fit cylinders to every single fibre in small cut- out datasets. Length, orientation and diameter of the cylinders act as input for the determination of accuracy of the developed CT data analysis method. By semi- automatic comparison of input and software output it was possible to identify correctly characterised fibres and the reasons for errors. Errors identified were virtual separation, wrong connection, the loss of very short fibres and some other minor effects that were subsumed to ‘other problems’. This analysis was performed for CT data with 1, 2 and 3 µm voxel edge length. The accuracy was defined as fraction of number of fibres that were extracted correctly with respect to the input number.

The result of CT data analysis using iAnalyse gives start and endpoint of each fibre. Both orientation and length can be calculated from these two points. The tensor can be visualized as ellipsoid which shows the orientation degree as to shape and the preferred fibre direction by the biggest principal axis. The orientation degree is quantified by an Eigenvalue analysis of the second order tensor and the normalization from 0 to 1:

$$O_D = (\lambda_{max} - 1/3) * 3/2 \quad (1)$$

2.3 2D Sectioning

Once the CT scans had been carried out, the same samples were then prepared for the 2D sectioning technique by encapsulating in epoxy and polishing. Previous work established that the best 2D plane for this technique is the one containing predominantly in-plane fibres, so the YZ plane was analysed at positions 2 and 4. Once polished, the surface was then plasma etched to give suitable contrast (see Fig. 4d below). The system works by scanning across the prepared 2D surface, in a raster fashion and at high magnification (x500), and determining the elliptical parameters for each fibre image. Typical fitted ellipses for the chosen area are also shown in Fig. 4d and this analysis allows the second order tensor values to be determined. This technique allows large areas (up to 40mm x 40mm) to be scanned and good counting statistics (usually over 104 fibres). The limit to this technique is that only four of the six second order tensor components can be determined from a 2D section, compared to the CT technique which measures all six. Details about the applied method can be found in [8].

3 RESULTS

3.1 2D and 3D data quality

Figure 2: CT slice images from axial and frontal direction at different voxel edge lengths: 1 µm (a), 2 µm (b) and 3 µm (c). Image (d) shows a light optical image at magnification 500 after polishing and with fitted ellipses below

Single fibre characterisation requires high quality data. Besides high resolution, noise and other artefacts have to be minimized and contrast maximized. The CT slice images in Fig. 2 indicate that for the investigated material system, 1 and 2 μm voxel edge length give very good data quality because single fibres can be identified and separated very well. At 3 μm voxel edge length all structures are blurred and fibres that are positioned very close together cannot be separated by eye everywhere. The zoom into a 2D LOM image in Fig. 2 (d) shows that this analysis leads to very high resolution and good image quality which is necessary for accurate ellipse fitting.

3.2 Accuracy of 3D CT data analysis

One of three datasets, containing approx. 250 fibres, is visualised in a 3D rendered view in Fig. 3a. The fitted cylinders are perfect reference geometries that are overlaid with the grey value CT data (Fig. 3b)

Figure 3: 3D renderings of CT data cut-out: original grey value (a), original + cylinders overlay (b) cylinders (c)

The results of the manual comparison of input and CT data analysis are shown in Table 1. By comparing the number of fibres that are extracted correctly (start-, endpoint and shape agree) with the input number, the accuracy is calculated. The orientation tensors in Table 1 are average values from the complete data sets.

Parameter	Input	Scan 1 μm	Scan 2 μm	Scan 3 μm
Fibre count	231	227	228	241
Correct fibre count	231	224	216	177
Accuracy (Input)	100 %	97.2 %	93.7 %	76.9 %
a_{xx}	0.130	0.127	0.126	0.129
a_{yy}	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.011
a_{zz}	0.861	0.865	0.865	0.860
a_{xy}	0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.003
a_{xz}	0.010	-0.071	-0.067	-0.063
a_{yz}	0.030	0.031	0.034	0.031
Strength of orientation	0.79	0.81	0.80	0.80
Separated		0.3	5.0	31.0
Wrongly connected		2.3	4.7	14.0
Other problems		3.7	5.0	8.3

Table 1: Values for accuracy and orientation tensor at different voxel edge length and input. Number of errors detected that determine accuracy. The values for the scans are averaged from three specimens.

3.3 Comparison of CT and sectioning method

The results of both methods for two positions of the sector sheet are given in Table 2. Average and standard deviation are calculated from three samples at each position. Every CT analysis contains ca. 76000 and every 2D sectioning analysis ca. 14500 fibres.

Tensor values over sheet thickness divided into 21 values are calculated additionally. Fig. 4 shows the main diagonal tensor elements (a_{XX} , a_{YY} and a_{ZZ}) for position 2 and 4. The error bars in Fig.4 (a, b, c and d) show maximum, minimum and average value. The overlay of CT and sectioning method can be seen in Fig.4 e and f.

		CT		2D sectioning		Difference
		Avg.	Stddev.	Avg.	Stddev.	Δ
Position 2	a_{XX}	0.285	0.005	0.278	0.014	0.007
	a_{YY}	0.012	0.000	0.014	0.001	-0.002
	a_{ZZ}	0.703	0.005	0.708	0.015	-0.005
	a_{YZ}	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
Position 4	a_{XX}	0.241	0.011	0.241	0.012	0.000
	a_{YY}	0.014	0.000	0.013	0.001	0.001
	a_{ZZ}	0.745	0.011	0.746	0.012	-0.001
	a_{YZ}	0.001	0.001	-0.003	0.005	0.005

Table 2: Orientation tensor elements from CT and sectioning showing average, standard deviation and difference between the two methods.

Figure 4: Main diagonal elements of the orientation tensor through sheet thickness for position 2 and 4. First column CT results (a, b), second column 2D sectioning (c, d) and third column overlay of both (e, f)

Fibre orientation over sheet thickness for the sector sheets in general shows the expected behaviour which is reported in literature [10-12]. Strong orientation in injection direction is observed in a region near the surface whereas weaker orientation and different direction is observed in the core region. The curves show symmetrical behaviour. At position 4, which is further away from the centre of the sheet in lateral direction, a different fibre direction in the core region, which is approx. 50°, is observed. This circumstance can be visualized by transferring tensor information into ellipsoids. For the regions 'near surface' and 'centre' the ellipsoids together with CT slice images are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Orientation determined by CT analyses in regions near surface and centre for position 2 and 4 showing slice images (XZ plane) and ellipsoids (XZ and YZ plane). The eigenvectors (ev1, ev2, ev3) are shown as principle axes. The colour of the ellipsoids gives orientation density O_D : near surface 0.93, 0.96 (position 2, 4); 0.81, 0.82 (position 2, 4)

4 DISCUSSION

The investigated methods for the determination of fibre orientation for short fibre reinforced polymers, CT and sectioning, both provide tensor data on fibre scale. This has the advantage of getting detailed information in a versatile format that can be used in the same way as flow simulation results for mechanical simulation. High resolution CT scans using laboratory equipment leads to adequate image quality in terms of sharpness, contrast, noise and artefacts. The 2D sectioning method has the advantage of higher resolution and very good contrast due to staining. For both methods suitable image processing tools have to be applied in order to achieve high accuracy and desired output format. For $2\ \mu\text{m}$ voxel edge length, which implies approx. 6 voxels for fibre diameter, an accuracy of almost 94 % was obtained using the in-house developed CT data analysis tool. At $3\ \mu\text{m}$ voxel edge length accuracy drops down to 77 %. Looking at the orientation tensor values even at lower resolution, only very small deviations from the desired input were found.

Orientation tensor show very similar results for both methods, with smaller standard for CT analysis. Standard deviation is not only determined by the method but also by manufacturing technique and material properties. The consideration of main diagonal tensor elements leads to conclusions about preferred fibre orientation if one element is almost one. Looking at the sample position 4 in the centre (Fig. 4), the X and Z component are almost equal. Without taking all 9 tensor elements into account two interpretations would be possible: high orientation density in 45° direction (X-Z plane) or low orientation density in arbitrary direction. [13] The visualization of the complete tensor leads to an ellipsoid (Fig. 5) its shape and preferred orientation can be linked to fibre orientation. The visual impression about fibre orientation which is received from the slice images is also seen in the orientation of the ellipsoids.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Results of a novel CT data analysis method show high accuracy for characterisation of fibre orientation. The influence of resolution depending on fibre diameter was investigated and lead to the conclusion, that approx. 6 voxels per diameter are necessary for accurate single fibre characterisation including length distribution. Orientation distribution can be determined accurately also at lower resolution. Since the complete second order tensor is determined, it is possible to refer the direction of fibre orientation to a given coordinate system and calculate the degree of orientation.

The standard method of sectioning and LOM analysis is well established and delivers results from one single plane with good statistics since several thousand fibres are being investigated. CT can provide information from a volume and is therefore well suited for objects or regions with very complex orientation distribution like weld lines. A-priori knowledge of fibre orientation is useful in both cases in order to achieve results with high accuracy. The comparison of both methods indicates that laboratory CT together with the developed data analysis method is a useful tool for the determination of fibre orientation that leads to valid results. The difference of all tensor components were below 0.007. Beyond that CT results allow directly for determination of length distribution.

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